

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of public service innovation, employee competence, community participation and accountability on the quality of public services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat

Saimara AM *, Sebayang, Febrilian Lestario, Husni Muharram Ritonga and Machyani Syafriani Indah Tanjung
Management Study Program, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 24(03), 3106-3119

Publication history: Received on 21 November 2024; revised on 30 December 2024; accepted on 31 December 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.3.4029>

Abstract

This research was conducted to find out and analyze the influence of Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability on the Quality of Public Service. The location of the research was carried out in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat Regency, North Sumatra. This research method uses a descriptive method with a quantitative approach. The sample used in this study was 100 people who were residents of Pematang Serai Village. The results of data processing were calculated using SPSS v 25 software. The results of the study show that partially Public Service Innovation has a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services. Employee Competence has a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services. Community Participation has a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services and Accountability has a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services. Meanwhile, simultaneously Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability together have a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services. The contribution to this research variable is only 48.0%.

Keywords: Public Service Innovation; Employee Competence; Community Participation; Accountability; Public Service Quality; Pematang Serai Village

1. Introduction

Village development has various interpretations which contain the meaning of village community development, where the connection of various government and community efforts with the aim and purpose of improving the standard of living and welfare of the community which includes several components [1]in [2]. The implementation of the Village Law was implemented starting in 2015. Rules on villages are regulated in which they contain village governance policies (Law Number 6, 2014) where these policies provide a great opportunity to improve the welfare of village communities (President of the Republic of Indonesia, 2014). These policies include the allocation of a large amount of village funds to all villages in Indonesia. A large amount of village funds have been budgeted by the government, every year the budgeting of village funds is always increased in accordance with the management carried out by the village government.

The government also made a Regulation of the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration (Kemendes PDTT) which says that the government's policy of delegating power to villages autonomously is to lay the foundation for development starting from the village level. Then it can be seen in the 5-Year National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJM), namely from 2015-2019 which gives a mandate to build Indonesia from the periphery and strengthen regions and villages. According to Swalem in [2] the development of village communities begins with a community approach such as community participation and its organization and

* Corresponding author: Saimara AM

implementation leading to community initiative and creativity. Village development has various interpretations which contain the meaning of village community development, where the connection of various government and community efforts with the aim and purpose of improving the standard of living and welfare of the community which includes several components [1]in [2].

The development of today's world has accelerated so quickly, technology has made the boundaries between information and human needs closer. This speed and accuracy are also needed in the process of interaction between the government and citizens, but unfortunately the high mobility of citizens is not balanced with the accuracy and speed of the government in terms of services, especially services to the public. Citizens have the right to get quality public services from the state (bureaucracy). Citizens also have the right to be protected for their rights, to have their voices heard, as well as to be respected for their values and preferences. Thus, citizens have the right to assess, reject and prosecute anyone who is politically responsible for the provision of public services. This concept is referred to as The New Public Service (NPS) which was developed by Janet V. Denhardt and Robert B. Denhardt in 2003. The performance of public services can be improved if there is an "exit" and "voice" mechanism. The "exit" mechanism means that if public services are not of good quality, consumers must have the opportunity to choose another public service provider that they prefer. Meanwhile, the "voice" mechanism means that there is an opportunity to express dissatisfaction to public service providers. This New Public Service Approach is in line with the "Exit" and "Voice" Theory which was previously developed by [4].

Villages and human resources are closely related to the desire to create quality and competent human resources in accordance with the needs of the community's environment. Competence can be interpreted as a person's observable abilities, such as knowledge, skills, and attitudes at the time of completing work and in accordance with the intention that is used as the goal [5] in [6]. In terms of the quality of human resources, rural areas have quite a lot of human resources that do not have quality compared to those that already have quality. At various scales, community participation related to education in local governments is still low, and this shows that professions in rural areas are still quite limited. Participation by the community can take the form of decision-making for the common good, so that the development carried out can be more directed. In addition, the form of community participation can be in the form of evaluation after implementing the entire plan intends and aims to find out the success rate of the plan that has been implemented so that there are no internal deviations [7]in [8].

In addition to community participation and competence, the role of village officials can also affect the accountability of village fund management. According to [9]the role is the position or position of a person in carrying out his obligations and rights based on the position he or she is in. The role of the village apparatus is a unit of the village government which is carried out by a number of village apparatus such as the village head, village secretary, village treasurer, and other apparatus to achieve goals in the village government [10]. If village officials can carry out all their duties properly and in accordance with applicable regulations, then the accountability of village fund management can be transparent and accountable.

Public services are the most visible benchmark of government performance. The public can directly assess the government's performance based on the services they receive. For this reason, the quality of public services in all ministries/institutions is a fundamental thing that must be improved immediately. Improving public services, the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform (KemenPAN RB) has implemented a policy that since 2014 is the year of public service innovation. All government agencies, both at the central and regional levels, are expected to be able to make a creative idea or answer to the way public services work/methods. The Ministry of Internal Affairs collects and assesses innovations that have been carried out in a number of agencies throughout Indonesia.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Quality of Public Services

2.1.1. Definition of Quality

Quality according to the Great Dictionary of the Indonesian Language is the level of good or bad of something, level, degree, or level, quality. In line with this understanding, according to [11]in [12], quality is conformance to requirement, that is, in accordance with what is required or standardized. The definition confirms that in a quality there is a certain measure or measure that is used as a reference for a product or service. The quality of a product is determined from the benchmark. It is said to be of quality if it is suitable or reaches the intended size, but if it is not suitable, it means that the product is lacking or not of quality. One of the measures of quality is from the expectations of customers or product

users. In this case, quality means meeting customer expectations. Furthermore, the concept is known as customer satisfaction.

Quality is a dynamic condition related to products, people/labor, processes and tasks as well as the environment that meets the expectations of customers or consumers according to [13]the [12]. Furthermore, Feigenbaum, stated that a product can be said to be of quality if it meets satisfaction or in accordance with what is expected by consumers. According to [14]in [15]the inside, quality is the basic strategy of a business that produces goods and services that meet the needs and satisfaction of internal and external consumers, explicitly and implicitly". Based on the description above, it can be concluded that there are two main things in the sense of quality, namely the first is the measure or size and the second is the expectation of customers or users of the product as a reference for the size in question. Therefore, in this study, what is meant by quality is a measure of the goodness or badness of a service product or service seen from its suitability with the expectations of the service user.

2.1.2. Definition of Public Service

Service is an activity or sequence of activities that occurs in direct interaction between a person and another person or a machine physically, and provides customer satisfaction. In the Great Dictionary of the Indonesian Language, it is explained that service is an effort to serve the needs of others. While serving is helping to prepare/take care of what a person needs. Service is an activity carried out by a person or group in providing satisfaction to service recipients. Service is essentially a series of activities, therefore service is a process. Service as a process takes place regularly and continuously covering all people's lives in society. According to [16], in his book entitled Public Service and Customer Satisfaction, it is defined as a series of activities or processes that meet the needs of others in a more satisfactory manner in the form of service products with a number of characteristics such as intangible, quickly lost, more perceptible than owned, and customers can more actively participate in the process of consuming these services.

Service is an activity in order to meet the needs of the community. Service has no form, but can be felt and quickly disappears. According to [17]the statement, service in a work organization is identical to the elaboration of the duties of the authorized employee/administrator in the organization concerned. Service means providing assistance, providing facilities, participation, and other meanings of providing assistance to others towards the achievement of goals.

According to Khairul Muluk in Retnowati WD Tuti, 2017 there are 5 (five) typologies of innovation in the public sector:

- Product/Service Innovation

Changes in the form and design of new products or services or updating existing services.

- Service Process Innovation

Continuous quality updates and refer to a combination of organizational changes, procedures, and policy needs to innovate.

- Innovation of service methods

New changes in terms of interacting with customers or new ways of delivering services.

- Policy Innovation

Referring to the new vision, mission, goals and strategies.

- System Innovation

New or updated ways of interacting with other actors, in other words, changes in governance.

2.2. Employee Competencies

Competence is one of the important components that individuals must have so that the implementation of work tasks can run well. According to [18]in [19]defining competence as an ability based on skills and knowledge supported by work attitudes and its application in carrying out tasks and work in the workplace that refer to the set work requirements. According to [20]in [21]the article, competence is more defined as the underlying characteristics of a person that are related to the effectiveness of an individual's work in his or her work. Meanwhile [22], it explains that

competence consists of a number of key behaviors needed to carry out a certain role to produce satisfactory achievements or performance.

Competency Indicators In this study, the indicators used to measure how much competence employees have, especially electromedical personnel in hospitals, are in accordance with the indicators used by [20]the [21]inside, namely:

- Achievement or proactive behavior. A person's drive or desire to act beyond what is required or demanded by the job and affects the improvement of his performance.
- Service or social awareness. Contains essence as sincerity in understanding the wants, interests and needs of others and including the needs of the person to be served. While social awareness is the ability to understand other people's emotions and other skills in treating others according to their reactions. Some of the things that are included in social awareness are empathy, orientation to service and organizational awareness.
- Ability to influence others. It contains essence as a person's ability to persuade, convince, and influence or make a good impression on others so that others are willing to support their ideas.
- Managerial skills. Includes competencies in developing others, directing skills, teamwork, and leadership in groups.
- Cognitive ability/mindset. The ability of the system to think and recognize a pattern. Cognitive ability has been the best general predictor of performance in various job professions.
- Self-awareness. The ability to recognize and understand one's own mood, emotions and their effects on others. These abilities include self-control, confidence, and flexibility that affect performance.

2.3. Community Participation

The implementation of an activity is inseparable from the goals to be achieved. The goal to be achieved, of course, must be supported and participated by each member, both mentally and emotionally. A person's involvement in an activity is a person's participation that we should respect, and it is hoped that there will be benefits and goals for the participation. Participation is characterized by the involvement of a person in a group, both moral and material, as well as a sense of responsibility. Etymologically, community participation comes from the Latin *pars* which means part and *capere*, which means to take, so it is interpreted as "taking part". In English, *participate* or *participation* means to take part or take a role. So it can be interpreted that participation is taking part or taking a role in the political activities or activities of a country.

In the Great Dictionary of Indonesian (KBBI), participation means that there is participation (supervising, controlling and influencing) the community in an activity ranging from planning to implementation evaluation. There are several concepts of participation explained in KBBI, namely:

- Participation as a policy, which is a concept that views participation as a producer of consultation by policymakers to the community as the subject of regional financial management,
- Participation as a strategy, namely to get public support for the credibility issued by the government.
- Participation as a means of communication, for the government (as a servant of the people) to know the wishes of the people.
- Participation as a tool for dispute resolution, a concept that sees participation as a tool for dispute resolution and tolerance for distrust and poisoning that exists in society.

2.4. Accountability

The concept of accountability is one of the elements that exists because of the difference in functions in the organization so that evaluation of separate tasks and performance is needed. Accountability exists with the reason that all parties involved understand the instructions to ensure that all things that have happened have been carried out properly [23] in [24].

Public accountability is the obligation of agents to manage resources, report, and disclose all activities and activities related to the use of public resources to the principal [25]. Public accountability is the provision of information on government activities and performance to interested parties. Accountability refers to the obligation of each individual, group or institution to fulfill the responsibilities entrusted to it. According to Sadjianto, Accountability is one of the main elements of the manifestation of good governance currently being pursued in Indonesia. The government is required to report the results of programs that have been implemented for the public to evaluate whether the government has worked economically, efficiently and effectively [26]. Every program that has been implemented by the government must be reported for the purpose of evaluating activities.

2.5. Research Methods

This study uses a quantitative approach method. According to [27] in [28], quantitative research is useful for collecting data on beliefs, opinions, characteristics, behaviors, and variable relationships in past or current contexts. The data collection technique through observation (interviews or questionnaires) is not too in-depth, and the results of the research tend to be generalized. The research was carried out in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat. This approach involves respondents in assessing public services, compensation, community participation and accountability as well as the quality of village services that have been carried out. Population involves all the values of calculations and measurements, both qualitatively and quantitatively, related to fully defined objects.

The population refers to the entire population of Pematang Serai Village, Langkat, which amounts to 849 heads of households. Meanwhile, the sample is a subset of the characteristics and number of the population. When the population is large and limited funds, time, and manpower hinder research on the entire population, then samples can be taken as a representation [28]. The sample is a representation or part of the population that is the focus of the research [29] in (Arikunto, 2019). Using the Slovin formula, the optimal number of samples can be determined based on the calculation of the number of respondents with a tolerance of error at the level of 15%, 10%, and 5%. From the calculation using the Slovin formula, it was found that the ideal sample size for this study was around 100 respondents with an error tolerance rate of 10%. Based on this, the researcher chose 100 people from Pematang Serai Village, Langkat as a research sample.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Description of the Research Object

This study aims to analyze the influence of Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat leading to efforts to improve the quality of public services in the village. The focus is to analyze how innovations in public services, the competence of employees who provide services, community participation in the service process, and the accountability of village governments affect the quality of public services felt by the community. This research covers several important dimensions. Public service innovations can be in the form of simplifying procedures, utilizing information technology, or creating new services that meet the needs of the community.

Table 1 Profile of Research Respondents

Information	Total	Percentage
Number of samples	100	100%
Gender:		
Man	52	52%
Woman	48	48%
Age:		
20-30 years old	14	14%
31-40 years old	63	63%
> 40 years	23	23%
Education:		
JUNIOR	31	31%
SMA	54	54%
THE	15	15%

Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

Employee competence includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of village officials in providing effective and professional services. Community participation is seen from their involvement in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public services. Meanwhile, accountability emphasizes transparency and accountability of the village government in managing resources and providing services to the community. The data source used in this study is in

the form of primary data from a questionnaire addressed to the people of Pematang Serai Village. The selection of this sample uses the Slovin formula which has been determined with several criteria. In this study, the analysis tool used is the SPSS v. 25 program.

Based on table 1., it is known that the number of male respondents is 52 people (52%) and female respondents are 48 people (48%). The number of respondents aged 20-30 years was 14 people (14%), 31-40 years old was 63 people (63%) and >40 years old. Meanwhile, respondents based on junior high school education were 31 people (31%), high school education as many as 54 people (54%) and S1 education as many as 15 people (15%).

3.2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The multiple regression analysis that has been carried out obtained the regression coefficient, t-value calculation and significance level as shown in the following table:

Table 2 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Coefficients ^a					
Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	17.927	3.060		5.858	0.000
Public Service Innovation	0.332	0.314	0.346	2.282	0.049
Employee Competencies	0.255	0.634	0.252	2.244	0.048
Community Participation	0.456	0.546	0.548	2.836	0.030
Accountability	0.812	0.409	0.797	2.985	0.010

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Public Services Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

From these results, the regression equation in the form of *standardized coefficient* is written as follows:

$$Y = 17.927 + 0.332 X_1 + 0.255 X_2 + 0.456 X_3 + 0.812 X_5 + e$$

Information:

- Y = Quality of Public Services
- X₁ = Public Service Innovation
- X₂ = Employee Competencies
- X₃ = Community Participation
- X₄ = Accountability
- e = Error
- α = Constant

Based on the results of the regression equation, it can be explained that the regression coefficient of the Public Service Innovation variable is obtained at 0.332 with a positive coefficient sign. This means that the stronger the influence of Public Service Innovation, the higher the Quality of Public Service. On the other hand, the weaker the influence of Public Service Innovation, the lower the quality of Public Service tends to be.

The regression coefficient of the Employee Competency variable was obtained at 0.255 with a positive coefficient sign. This means that the stronger the influence of Employee Competence, the higher the Quality of Public Services. On the other hand, the weaker the influence of Public Service Innovation, the lower the quality of Public Service tends to be.

The regression coefficient of the Community Participation variable was obtained at 0.456 with a positive coefficient sign. This means that the stronger the influence of Community Participation, the higher the quality of Public Services. On the contrary, the weaker the influence of Community Participation, the lower the quality of Public Services tends to be.

The regression coefficient of the Accountability variable was obtained at 0.812 with a positive coefficient sign. This means that the stronger the influence of Accountability, the higher the Quality of Public Services. On the other hand, the weaker the influence of Accountability, the lower the quality of public services.

3.3. Classical Assumption Test

The classical assumption test is used as a condition in using the regression model so that the regression results obtained are accurate estimates.

3.3.1. Normality Test

The normality test is useful to test whether in the regression model, the dependent variable and the independent variable have a normal distribution or not. The normality test in this study uses the distribution on the P-P plot graph. The following are the results of the normality test using the P-P Plot graph using the help of the SPSS version 25 application.

Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

Figure 1 P-P Plot Chart

Based on figure 1 above, it can be seen that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line on the histogram, this shows that the distribution pattern is normal. So it can be concluded that based on the P-P plot graph, the regression model satisfies the assumption of normality.

3.3.2. Multicollinearity Test

The Multicollinearity Test is useful to test whether the regression model finds a correlation between independent variables. The way to find out whether there is a deviation in the multicollinearity test is to look at the Tolerance and VIF values of each independent variable, if the Tolerance value > 0.10 and the VIF value < 10 , then the data is free from multilinearity symptoms.

Looking at the results in table 3, the results of the calculation of the Tolerance value are no independent variables that have a Tolerance value of less than 0.10 with the Tolerance value of each independent variable having a value of Public Service Innovation of 0.819, Employee Competency of 0.822, Community Participation of 0.820 and Accountability by 0.854. Meanwhile, the results of the calculation of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value also show the same thing, namely the absence of a VIF value from an independent variable that has a VIF value of more than 10 with the VIF value of each independent variable is Public Service Innovation of 1,138, Employee Competence is 1,787, Community Participation is 1,686 and Accountability amounted to 1,679. Referring to the results of the calculation of Tolerance and VIF values, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a			
Type		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Public Service Innovation	0.819	1.138
	Employee Competencies	0.822	1.787
	Community Participation	0.820	1.686
	Accountability	0.854	1.679

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Public Services Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

3.3.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test in the regression model that there is a variance inequality from the residual of one observation to another. The way to find out whether heteroscedasticity occurs or not is by looking at the Plot Graph between the prediction value of the dependent variable, namely ZPRED and the residual SRESID. There is no heteroscedasticity, i.e. when there is no clear pattern, and the dots spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis

Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

Figure 2 Scatterplot Charts

Based on figure 2 above, it can be seen that there is no clear pattern and the dots spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis.

3.4. Hypothesis Test

3.4.1. Partially Test

The t-test was used to test whether the independent variable had a significant effect on the bound variable. The significance rate used is 5% [30]. The test criteria in the t-statistical test were carried out by comparing the calculated t-value with the t-table value using a significance level of 5%. If the tcal value is greater than the ttable, then individually the independent variable affects the dependent variable. In addition, it can also be done by looking at the probability value. If the probability value is less than 0.05 (for significance level = 5%), then the independent variable individually

affects the dependent variable. Meanwhile, if the probability value is greater than 0.05, then the *independent variable* individually has no effect on the dependent variable. The following are the results of the calculation of the t-test in the following table:

Table 4 Partial Test Results (t-Test)

Coefficients ^a						
Type		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	17.927	3.060		5.858	0.000
	Public Service Innovation	0.332	0.314	0.346	2.282	0.049
	Employee Competencies	0.255	0.634	0.252	2.244	0.048
	Community Participation	0.456	0.546	0.548	2.836	0.030
	Accountability	0.812	0.409	0.797	2.985	0.010

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Public Services Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

Based on the results of data processing in table 4., it shows that the tcount is 2,282 and the ttable is 1.66023, so that the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ and seen from the level of significance the Public Service Innovation variable has a value of 0.049 < from a significant value of 0.05 so that it can be concluded that the Public Service Innovation used in the study has a significant positive effect on Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat.

The results of the processing show that the tcount is 2,244 and the ttable is 1.66023, so the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ and seen from the level of significance of the Employee Competency variable has a value of 0.048 < from a significant value of 0.05 so that it can be concluded that the Employee Competency used in the study has a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat.

The results of the processing show that the tcount is 2,836 and the ttable is 1.66023, so the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ and seen from the level of significance of the Community Participation variable has a value of 0.030 < from a significant value of 0.05 so that it can be concluded that the Community Participation used in the research has a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat.

The results of the processing show that the tcount is 2,985 and the ttable is 1.66023, so the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ and seen from the level of significance the Accountability variable has a value of 0.010 < from a significant value of 0.05 so that it can be concluded that the Accountability used in the study has a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat.

3.4.2. Test Simultaneously

The F test is used to test the independent variables together against the bound variables. The following is a table of F test results with statistical calculations using SPSS v 25, as follows:

Table 5 Simultaneous Test Results (Test F)

ANOVA ^a						
Type		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	196.493	4	49.123	5.205	0.001b
	Residual	896.497	95	9.437		
	Total	1092.990	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Public Services; b. Predictors: (Constant), Accountability, Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

Based on the table of test results with the F test above, it was obtained that the F-calculation number between Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability to the bound variables, namely

customer satisfaction of 5,205 and a probability value of 0.001 is greater than the significance level of 5% or 0.05, meaning that the variable Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability together have a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat and the regression model in this study is said to be feasible.

3.4.3. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The determination coefficient essentially measures how far the model is able to explain the variation that occurs in the dependent variable. The value of the determination coefficient is between zero and one [30]. The value of the determination coefficient is determined through the adjusted R square value as shown in the following table.

Table 6 Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model Summary ^b				
Type	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.424 ^a	0.480	0.345	3.07194

a. Predictors: (Constant), Accountability, Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation; b. Dependent Variable: Quality of Public Services Source: SPSS Output Results v 24, 2024

Based on table 6 above, the results of the analysis show that the *Adjusted R Square* value is 0.480. This means that the variables of Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability have a contribution of 48.0% in explaining the Quality of Public Services. Meanwhile, other factors that were not studied in this study that affect customer satisfaction had a contribution of (100% - 48.0%) = 6.6%.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Influence of Public Service Innovation on the Quality of Public Services

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis used to test the influence of the Public Service Innovation variable on the Quality of Public Services, it shows that the *t*-count is 2.282 and the *t*-table is 1.66023, so that the *t*-count > *t*-table and seen from the level of significance the Public Service Innovation variable has a value of 0.049 < 0.05 so that it can be concluded that Public Service Innovation used in the study had a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat. Innovations made in public services in the village, such as simplifying procedures, using technology, or improving accessibility, have a real impact on improving the quality of services received by the community. This quality improvement can be in the form of faster, easier, transparent, and responsive services to the needs of the community.

In addition, the significance level of the Public Service Innovation variable of 0.049 which is below the significance value of 0.05 further strengthens the conclusion that the innovations carried out do have a real influence, not due to coincidence factors. Based on the Reinventing Government Theory, it emphasizes the importance of the government to continue to innovate in order to provide better, efficient, and responsive public services to the needs of the community. Innovation in public services is seen as the key to creating good governance. The Public Service Motivation Theory explains that the intrinsic motivation of public officials to serve the community can be increased through innovation. With innovation, public officials will feel more challenged and motivated to produce quality public services.

Research conducted by [31] In their research on SERVQUAL, they found that innovation is one of the important dimensions that affect the quality of service. Innovation in service can increase public perception of the quality of services received. Research conducted by [32] states that innovation in the public sector is a must to respond to dynamic environmental changes and improve the effectiveness of public services. Research conducted by [33] shows that public service innovation has a significant effect on the quality of public services in the city of Bandung.

The results of this study show the importance of innovation in public services to increase community satisfaction and realize good governance. The Pematang Serai Village Government can continue to develop innovations in public services in order to be able to answer the needs and challenges that develop in the community.

4.2. The Effect of Employee Competence on the Quality of Public Services

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis used to test the influence of the Competency variable on the Quality of Public Services, it shows that the t_{count} is 2.244 and the t_{table} is 1.66023, so that the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ and seen from the level of significance the Employee Competency variable has a value of 0.048 < from a significant value of 0.05 so that it can be concluded that the Employee Competency used in the study had a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat. The competencies possessed by employees, such as knowledge, skills, and attitudes in providing services, have a real impact on improving the quality of services received by the community. Competent employees are able to provide more professional, effective, and in accordance with community expectations. The significance level of the Employee Competency variable of 0.048 which is below the significance value of 0.05 shows that the positive influence of employee competence on the quality of public services is not a coincidence, but has a strong basis.

This research is supported by the Human Capital Theory which emphasizes the importance of investing in human resources, including improving employee competence, to achieve organizational goals. Competent employees are seen as valuable assets that can improve productivity and service quality. Resource Theory which states that an organization's competitive advantage is determined by the resources it has, including employee competencies. Superior employee competence can be a differentiator and create added value in public services.

This research is supported by research conducted by [34] In his research on the influence of employee competence on the quality of public services in Belgium, it was found that employee competence has a significant effect on public satisfaction with public services. Research conducted by [35] shows that the quality of service is greatly influenced by the quality of interaction between employees and the community. Employee competence, especially in terms of communication and interpersonal, is essential to create positive interactions and increase community satisfaction. Research conducted by [36] In her book "Human Resources and Work Productivity", Sedarmayanti explained that competence is a key factor that determines employee performance. Competent employees will be able to carry out their duties well and produce optimal performance, including in providing public services.

The results of this study emphasize the importance of improving employee competence in an effort to improve the quality of public services. The Pematang Serai Village Government needs to pay attention to employee competency improvement programs, such as training, technical guidance, and certification, so that employees can continue to improve the quality of performance and provide public services that satisfy the community.

4.3. The Effect of Community Participation on the Quality of Public Services

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis used to test the influence of the Community Participation variable on the Quality of Public Services, it shows that the t_{count} is 2.836 and the t_{table} is 1.66023, so that the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ and seen from the level of significance the Community Participation variable has a value of 0.030 < from a significant value of 0.05 so it can be concluded that Community participation used in the study had a significant positive effect on the quality of public services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat.

Active community participation, such as providing input, suggestions, and participating in the supervision of public services, has a real impact on improving the quality of services provided. Community participation allows village governments to better understand the needs and expectations of the community, so that they can provide more targeted and satisfactory services. This research is supported by the Participatory Democracy Theory which emphasizes the importance of active community involvement in the public decision-making process, including in the planning and supervision of public services. Community participation is seen as a manifestation of people's sovereignty and can increase government accountability and responsiveness. Good Governance Theory One of the main principles of good governance is participation. Community participation is needed to create a government system that is transparent, accountable, and responsive to the needs of the community.

Research conducted by [37] on co-production of public services, Bovaird found that community participation can improve the efficiency, effectiveness, and quality of public services. Research conducted by [38] states that community participation in the provision of public services can increase community satisfaction and create a sense of ownership of public services. Research conducted by [39] shows that community participation has a significant effect on the quality of public services in Sidoarjo Regency.

The results of this study are in line with previous theories and research that show that community participation is an important factor in improving the quality of public services. The Pematang Serai Village Government needs to continue

to increase community participation through various mechanisms, such as deliberative forums, suggestion boxes, and social media, in order to provide better quality public services in accordance with the needs of the community.

4.4. The Effect of Accountability on the Quality of Public Services

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis used to test the influence of the Accountability variable on the Quality of Public Services, it shows that the t_{count} is 2.985 and the t_{table} is 1.66023, so that the $t > t_{\text{table}}$ and seen from the level of significance the Accountability variable has a value of $0.010 < 0.05$ so that it can be concluded that the Accountability variable used in the study had a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat. The application of accountability principles in public services, such as transparency, accountability, and clarity of rules, has a real impact on improving the quality of services felt by the community. Accountability ensures that public services are carried out in accordance with the set standards and meet the expectations of the community.

In addition, the significance level of the Accountability variable of 0.010 which is below the significance value of 0.05 further emphasizes that the positive influence of accountability on the quality of public services is not a coincidence, but has a strong basis. These results are supported by Agency Theory which explains the relationship between principal (community) and agent (government). Accountability is required for agents to be accountable to the principal for their actions. In the context of public services, accountability guarantees that the government is responsible to the community for the quality of services provided. The theory of Good Governance which explains Accountability is one of the main principles in good governance. Accountability creates transparency, prevents abuse of power, and increases public trust in the government.

The results of this study are in line with [40] research on accountability in the public sector, Dubnick found that accountability has a significant effect on the quality of public services. Accountability increases government responsiveness to community needs and reduces corruption. Research by [41] states that accountability is a key factor in creating effective and efficient public services. Accountability encourages governments to use resources optimally and avoid waste. [42] research shows that accountability has a significant effect on the quality of public services in the city of Surabaya.

The results of this study show the importance of applying the principle of accountability in every aspect of public services to increase public trust and realize good governance. The Pematang Serai Village Government needs to continue to increase accountability in public services through various efforts, such as increasing information transparency, providing a public complaint mechanism, and evaluating public service performance periodically.

4.5. The Influence of Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability on the Quality of Public Services

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis used to test the influence of the variables Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability on Public Service Quality, the F_{cal} number between Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability was obtained to the bound variables, namely customer satisfaction of 5,205 and a probability value of 0.001 greater than the significance level of 5% or 0.05, meaning that the variables of Public Service Innovation, Employee Competence, Community Participation and Accountability together have a significant positive effect on the Quality of Public Services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat and the regression model in this study is said to be feasible. The combination of innovation in service, good employee competence, active community participation, and the application of accountability principles has a real impact in improving the quality of public services in Pematang Serai Village. With a significant F_{cal} value, it can be concluded that the regression model used in this study is feasible and acceptable. This model is able to explain the relationship between the independent variables (innovation, competence, participation, and accountability) and the bound variables (quality of public services).

The results of this study provide important information for village governments in formulating strategies to improve the quality of public services. The village government needs to pay attention to all variables that have been proven to have a significant effect, namely by continuing to develop service innovation, improving employee competence, encouraging community participation, and strengthening accountability in every aspect of service. This research shows the importance of a holistic approach in improving the quality of public services. It is not enough to focus on just one aspect, but it is necessary to pay attention to all the influencing factors simultaneously. Thus, efforts to improve the quality of public services will be more effective and sustainable

5. Conclusion

The results of this study are that there is a significant positive influence between public service innovation, employee competence, community participation, and accountability on the quality of public services in Pematang Serai Village, Langkat. Efforts to improve the quality of public services in the village need to be carried out comprehensively by paying attention to these four aspects. Village governments need to continue to innovate in providing services, improve the competence of village officials, encourage active community participation, and apply the principle of accountability in every aspect of service. Thus, it is hoped that the people of Pematang Serai Village can experience more quality, efficient, easy, and satisfactory public services.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] A. Amrullah, *Islamic Da'wah and Social Change: A Framework of Approaches and Problems*, Cet. 1st, A collection of writings at the national seminar and discussion of the Center for Community Training, Research and Development (PLP2M). Yogyakarta: Prima Duta, 1983.
- [2] R. Saragih and S. Agung, *The Role of Government Political Communication in UpayIncreasing Community Participation in the Utilization of Village Funds*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 59–69, 2017.
- [3] *Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6, About Villages*, 2014.
- [4] A. O. Hirschman, *Economic Development Strategy*, PT Dia Rakjat, Yayasan Dana Buku Indonesia. Sitohang's Translation, Paul, Jakarta, 1970.
- [5] A. I. Faried, U. Hasanah, R. Sembiring, and R. R. Agustin, "Pillars of Economic Development through MSMEs as an Opportunity for Labor Absorption in Indonesia," *AKMAMI Journal: Accounting, Management, Economics*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 570–579, 2021.
- [6] V. Rivai, *Human Resource Management for Companies*, 2nd Edition. Jakarta: Rajawali Press, 2018.
- [7] J. Cohen, "Quantitative Methods in Psychology: A Power Primer," *Psychol Bull*, vol. 112, no. 1, pp. 155–159, 1992.
- [8] Naimah, "Factors Affecting Village Financial Accountability in the Government of Serdang Bedagai Regency," *University of North Sumatra, Medan*, 2017.
- [9] S. Soekanto, *Introduction to Legal Research*. Jakarta: UI-Pers, 1986.
- [10] P. D. Anggraeni and N. L. Yuliani, "The Influence of Human Resource Competence, Information Technology Utilization, Budgeting Participation, Supervision and the Role of Village Apparatus on Village Fund Management (Empirical Study on Villages in Kajoran District)," in *In UMMagelang Conference Series*, 2019, pp. 266–284.
- [11] P. B. Crosby, *Quality is Free: The Art of Making Quality Certain*. New York: Mcgraw Hill, 1979.
- [12] M. N. Nasution, *Integrated Quality Management: Total Quality Management*, First Print. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia, 2001.
- [13] D. A. Garvin, *Managing Quality: The Strategic and Competitive Edge*. New York: Free Press, 1987.
- [14] B. Ibrahim, *TQM, A Guide to Facing the Global Market*. Jakarta: Djambatan, 1997.
- [15] A. Wahyuningsih, "Analysis of Consumer Satisfaction Level Based on Service Quality at Karanganyar Regency General Hospital," *UMS, Surakarta*, 2002.
- [16] P. Napitupulu, *Public Service & Costomer Satisfaction*. Bandung: PT Alumni, 2007.
- [17] S. Sastrodiningrat, *Human Behavior at Work*. Jakarta: UT Press, 2002.

- [18] S. Sebayang, "Developing Risk Management and Improving Risk Culture in Islamic Banking (Case Study: Bank Muamalat Period 2009-2013 and 2014-2018)," *JUMANT: Journal Management*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 181–197, 2020.
- [19] E. Sutrisno, *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2019.
- [20] L. M. Spencer and S. M. Spencer, "Competence at Work, Models For Superior Performance," Canada: John Wiley & Sons, Inc, 1993.
- [21] D. A. Triastuti, "The Influence of Work Environment, Competence and Organizational Climate on Employee Performance," *Journal of Management Review*, vol. 2, no. 2, p. 203, 2019.
- [22] D. Rusvitawati, T. Sugiati, and D. M. Sari, "The Effect of Competence on Employee Performance of Sari Mulia Hospital Banjarmasin," *JWM: Journal of Management Insights*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 1, 2019.
- [23] M. M. Sari, P. B. Sari, and S. H. Pohan, "Financial Performance of MSMEs: Financial Literacy and Inclusion," Medan: Stindo Press, 2023.
- [24] I Gede Sanica, P. C. Ayu, and I Made Suidarma, "A New Paradigm of Financial Accountability: An Institutional Review of the Subak Jatiluwih Tabanan Bali Organization, ed. Eric Vega," Jember: Pustaka Abadi, 2019.
- [25] A. Yunita and Mrs Christianingrum, "Measurement of Accountability Management of Village Funds," *Integrated Journal of Business and Economics*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 100, 2018.
- [26] A. Iswahyudi, I. Triyuwono, and M. Achsin, "The Relationship between Understanding Accountability, Transparency, Participation, Value For Money and Good Governance (Empirical Study on SKPD in Lumajang Regency)," *Scientific Journal of Accounting*, vol. 1, no. 2, p. 157, 2017.
- [27] E. D. Yanti, M. M. Sari, and N. Sihombing, "Improving the Quality of Human Resources and Economy of the Community of Kwala Serapuh Village through Local Economy-Based Education," *Journal of Social Responsibility Projects by Higher Education Forum*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 96–100, 2023.
- [28] Sugiyono, *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta, 2018.
- [29] M. T. Daulay and A. Sanny, "Analysis of Structural Equation Modeling Towards Productivity and Welfare of Farmer's Household in Sub-District Finish of Langkat Regency," *International Journal of Research & Review*, vol. 6, no. 11, pp. 117–123, 2019.
- [30] I. Ghozali, *Multivariate Analysis Applications with IBM SPSS 25 Program*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Press, 2018.
- [31] A. Parasuraman, A. V. Zeithaml, and L. L. Berry, "Delivering Service Quality: Balancing Customer Perceptions and Expectations," New York: Free Press, 1990.
- [32] J. V. Denhardt and Robert B. Denhardt, "The New Public Service: Serving, Not Steering," London, England: M.E. Sharpe, 2003.
- [33] D. Wulandari, "The Influence of Product Innovation (Relative Advantage, Compatibility and Compatibility) on BRI Mobile Banking User Intentions". (Study on 3 kg LPG Agent in Bandar Lampung)," *Faculty of Economics and Business, Lampung*, 2017.
- [34] J. A Van De Walle, "Elementary and Secondary Schools of Mathematics Development and Teaching (Suyono Translation)," Jakarta: Erlangga, 2007.
- [35] C. Gronroos, "A Service Quality Model And Its Marketing Implications," *Eur J Mark*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 36–45, 1984.
- [36] Sedarmayanti, *Human Resource Management, Bureaucratic Reform and Civil Servant Management*. Bandung: Refika Aditama, 2017.
- [37] T. Bovaird and E. Loffler, "Public Management and Governance," London: Routledge, 2003.
- [38] A. Fung and E. O. Wright, "Deepening Democracy: Institutional Innovations in Empowered Participatory Governance," London, New York: Verso, 2003.
- [39] I. Islamic, *Principles of State Policy Formulation*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2010.
- [40] M. Dubnick, "Accountability and The Promise of Performance: In Search of the Mechanisms," *Public Performance and Management Review*, Vol. 28, No. 3, pp. 376–417, 2005.
- [41] C. Pollitt and G. Bouckaert, "Public Management Reform: A Comparative Analysis, 2nd," Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004.
- [42] S. Andriani, "Analysis of the Quality of Administrative Services at Madrasah Aliyah Nahdlatul Ulama' 01 Banyuputih Batang Regency," Semarang State University, Semarang, 2015.